

Change Log: CoreTrustSeal Requirements 2023-2025

v01.00

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Introduction

To maintain alignment with practice and to ensure the requirements meet community needs, the CoreTrustSeal Requirements and supporting guidance are subject to feedback and revision every three years. The new Requirements will be in place from 2023-2025, all existing certifications under previous requirements remain valid until due for renewal.

The CoreTrustSeal mission continues to be provision of a low barrier to entry 'core' level of requirements that is broadly applicable to repository data service providers that ensure the long term preservation of the digital objects they curate for the benefit of a defined designated community.

This change log document accompanies the release (2022-09) of the revised CoreTrustSeal Requirement for 2023-2025. It describes the changes implemented based on Board proposals and community feedback.

The changes proposed by the Board based on their experience of certifying against the Requirements were overwhelmingly supported by community feedback. The Guidance has been editorially reviewed for additional clarity, to minimise perceived overlap between Requirements, and with an international audience in mind. Many of the excellent proposals received during the feedback period have been incorporated into the Guidance where they were within the scope of a 'core' Requirements set. Some proposals were not incorporated due to being too challenging for the broad range of repositories, or too domain or disciplinary specific to be included in the guidance. There were some proposals for which there is not yet sufficient community consensus for integration; some of these will form part of future CoreTrustSeal work to identify and address community priorities for clarification. These areas for future work include additional alignment with the FAIR Data Principles, definitions of 'levels of preservation' and the differing expectations of specialist and generalist repositories.

Synopsis of Changes

The diagram below provides an overview of changes to the short Requirements text and to the structure of CoreTrustSeal. This is intended to provide an easy reference point for those renewing their CoreTrustSeal applications, and to support comparison between assessments undertaken against different versions of the requirements. The remainder of this document follows the latest CoreTrustSeal Requirements text and structure.

CoreTrustSeal retains a 'core' level focus and expects the evidence necessary to achieve CoreTrustSeal to remain stable. Requirement names have been revised for clarity. Integrity measures are united with Storage under Storage & Integrity (R14).

The CoreTrustSeal Compliance levels have been simplified to:

- In Progress: the repository is in the implementation phase
- Implemented: the requirement has been fully implemented by the repository

Applicants may still find it useful to use the additional previous compliance levels during internal self-assessments: “The Repository has not considered this yet” and “the repository has a theoretical concept”.

In cases where the scope was too narrowly focussed on ‘data’, the use of the term ‘digital object’ has been expanded and used, alongside “data and metadata”.

In R0. Context the previous repository typology has been replaced by a free text option and a request to select either ‘specialist’ or ‘generalist’. Specialist repositories are asked to clarify their specialist scope.

Diagram: Synopsis of Changes to Short Requirements Text and Structure

Context (R0)

R0. Background Information & Context

This section provides the information necessary for reviewers to fully assess the applicants response statements. It is important to the entire application that the correct

options are selected and that sufficiently detailed responses are provided.

(1) Re3data Identifier2.

(2) Repository type. Select a repository type:

- **Generalist repository**
- **Specialist repository**
- **Specialist repositories are asked to provide their domain(s) and/or discipline(s).**

(3) Overview. Provide a short overview of key characteristics of the repository, reflecting the repository type selected. This should include information about the scope and size of data collections, data types and formats. Further contextual information may also be added.

(4) Designated Community. A clear definition of the Designated Community demonstrates that the applicant understands the scope, knowledge base, and methodologies—including preferred software/formats—of the group(s) of users at whom the curation and preservation measures are primarily targeted. The definition should be specific so that reviewers can assess whether that community is being served in the responses to other requirements.

(5) Levels of Curation.

Select all relevant types from:

- A. Content distributed as deposited**
- B. Basic curation – e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation**
- C. Enhanced curation – e.g. conversion to new formats during ingest, enhancement of documentation and metadata**
- D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data**

(6) Cooperation and outsourcing to third parties, partners and host organisations.

(7) Applicants renewing their CoreTrustSeal certification: summary of significant changes since last application. CoreTrustSeal certification has an expectation of continuous improvement over time. Repositories undergoing recertification should highlight briefly any significant changes including to technical systems, Designated Community or funding during the previous three years. This could include any steps taken to move from 'In Progress' to 'Implemented' Requirements since the last certification.

Was: R0. Please provide context for your repository.

– Repository Type. Select all relevant types from:

- Domain or subject-based repository
- Institutional repository
- National repository system, including governmental
- Publication repository
- Library
- Museum
- Archive
- Research project repository
- Other (Please describe)

– *Brief Description of Repository*

– *Brief Description of the Designated Community*

– *Level of Curation Performed. Select all relevant types from:*

A. Content distributed as deposited

B. Basic curation – e.g., brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation

C. Enhanced curation – e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation

D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy

Comments

– *Insource/Outsource Partners. If applicable, please list them.*

- Summary of Significant Changes Since Last Application (if applicable)

- Other Relevant Information

(1) Repository Type. This item will help reviewers understand what function your repository performs. Choose the best match for your repository type (select all that apply). If none of the categories is appropriate, feel free to provide another descriptive type. You may also provide further details to help the reviewer understand your repository type.

(2) Brief Description of Repository. Provide a short overview of the repository; in particular, please add information on the type of data accepted by the repository (i.e., the scope of its collection). If the repository has outsource partners, is part of a network, or of a parent organization, the response should ideally include a diagram and description of the overarching organizational structure.

(3) Designated Community. A clear definition of the Designated Community demonstrates that the applicant understands the scope, knowledge base, and methodologies—including preferred software/formats—of the user community or communities they are targeting. Please make sure that the response is sufficiently specific to enable reviewers to assess the adequacy of the curation and preservation measures described throughout the application.

(4) Level of Curation. This item is intended to elicit whether the repository distributes its content to data consumers without any changes, or whether the repository adds value by enhancing the content in some way. All levels of curation assume initial deposits are retained unchanged and that edits are only made on copies of those originals. Annotations/edits must fall within the terms of the license agreed with the data producer and be clearly within the skillset of those undertaking the curation. Thus, the repository will be expected to demonstrate that any such annotations/edits are undertaken and documented by appropriate experts and that the integrity of all original copies is maintained. Knowing this will help reviewers in assessing other certification Requirements. Further details can be added that would help to understand the levels of curation you undertake.

(5) Insource/Outsource Partners. Please provide a list of Partners that your organization works with, describing the nature of the relationship (organizational, contractual, etc.), and whether the Partner has undertaken any trustworthy repository assessment. If a function or supporting evidence is not under the direct control of the applicant then it falls into this category. This may be with a host organization or other 'insourcing' relationship, or through outsourcing or other dependency on a third-party. Such relationships may include, but are not limited to: any services provided by an institution you are part of, storage provided by others as part of multicopy redundancy, or membership in organizations that may undertake stewardship of your data collection when a business continuity issue arises. Moreover, please list the certification requirements for which the Partner provides all, or part of, the relevant functionality/service, including any contracts or Service Level Agreements in place. Because outsourcing will almost always be partial, you will still need to provide appropriate evidence for certification Requirements that are not outsourced and for the parts of the data lifecycle that you control.

Qualifications/certifications—including, but not limited to, the CoreTrustSeal certification (and its predecessors)—are preferred for outsource partners. However, it is not a necessity for them to be certified. We understand that this can be a complex area to define and describe, but such details are essential to ensure a comprehensive review process.

(6) Summary of Significant Changes Since Last Application. CoreTrustSeal certification has an expectation of continuous improvement. Repositories undergoing recertification should highlight briefly to the reviewers any significant changes in technical systems, Designated Community, funding, and so on during the previous three years. In doing so, please refer to any comments given to you by the reviewers of your previous CoreTrustSeal application. Detailed information on a change should be added to the appropriate Requirement.

(7) Other Relevant Information. The repository may wish to add extra contextual information that is not covered in the Requirements but that may be helpful to the reviewers in making their assessment. For example, you might describe:

- The usage and impact of the repository data holdings (citations, use by other projects, etc.).
- A national, regional, or global role that the repository serves.
- Any global cluster or network organization that the repository belongs to.

Context the previous repository typology has been replaced by a free text option and a request to select either 'specialist' or 'generalist'. Specialist repositories are asked to clarify their specialist scope.)

Organizational Infrastructure

Mission & Scope (R01)

R01. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve digital objects.

Was: 1. Mission/Scope. R1. The repository has an explicit mission to provide access to and preserve data in its domain.

Rights Management (R02)

R02. The repository maintains all applicable rights and monitors compliance.

Was: 2. Licenses. R2. The repository maintains all applicable licenses covering data access and use and monitors compliance.

Updated to reflect the fact that rights management goes beyond the traditional signing of a license agreement at the point of deposit or access and includes all the measures necessary to manage the permission, prohibitions and obligations of all actors involved in managing data and metadata. Many digital objects have some rights attached even if there is no license artifact as traditionally understood.

Continuity of Service (R03)

R03. The Repository has a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its data and metadata.

Was: 3. Continuity of access. R3. The repository has a continuity plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of its holdings.

This change more accurately reflects the scope of the requirement as covering ongoing services offered by the repository including access but also measures to ensure ongoing preservation. Avoids possible confusion with Access in the sense used by the FAIR Principles.

Legal & Ethical (R04)

R04. The repository ensures to the extent possible that data and metadata are created, curated, preserved, accessed and used in compliance with legal and ethical norms.

Was: 4. Confidentiality/Ethics. R4. The repository ensures, to the extent possible, that data are created, curated, accessed, and used in compliance with disciplinary and ethical norms.

This change highlights that many data protection measures are legally as well as ethically governed. This was already covered in the guidance text but is made more explicit. There is a stronger focus on evidence that demonstrates the applicants understanding of the legal and ethical framework they work within. References to 'discipline' have been adjusted to support a wider range of applicants. There is clearer separation of general guidance from that related to digital objects with a disclosure risk.

Governance & Resources (R05)

R05. The repository has adequate funding and sufficient numbers of staff managed through a clear system of governance to effectively carry out the mission.

Was: 5. Organizational infrastructure. R5. The repository has adequate funding and sufficient numbers of qualified staff managed through a clear system of governance to effectively carry out the mission.

This change more accurately reflects the scope of the Requirement. Potential overlap is avoided by adjusting references to qualifications and expertise that are more appropriate to Expertise and Guidance (R06) below.

Expertise & Guidance (R06)

R06. The repository adopts mechanisms to secure ongoing expertise, guidance and feedback- either in-house, or external.

Was: 6. Expert guidance. R6. The repository adopts mechanism(s) to secure ongoing expert guidance and feedback (either in-house, or external, including scientific guidance, if relevant).

This requirement will now include any guidance on internal or external expertise previously included under Governance & Resources (R05). The reference to scientific guidance is removed from the long requirement text and included in the guidance.

Digital Object Management

Provenance and authenticity (R07)

R07. The repository guarantees the authenticity of the digital objects and provides provenance information.

Was: 7. Data integrity and authenticity

R7. The repository guarantees the integrity and authenticity of the data.

This change focusses the requirement on measures to manage planned change. It was clear from previous applications that the topic of integrity was addressed primarily in technical terms. Integrity measures are now addressed alongside storage under Technical and Security, see Storage & Integrity (R14). The Board proposes to retain the R07 focus on authenticity and to address integrity measures alongside storage (see R09) under the Technology subsection of CoreTrustSeal.

Deposit & Appraisal (R08)

R08. The repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for users.

Was: 8. Appraisal. R8. The repository accepts data and metadata based on defined criteria to ensure relevance and understandability for data users.

This change reflects the focus on the appraisal and assessment of data and metadata at the point they are offered to a repository. Re-appraisal of digital objects over time is included under Preservation Plan (R09)

Preservation plan (R09)

R09. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way.

Was: 10. Preservation plan. R10. The repository assumes responsibility for long-term preservation and manages this function in a planned and documented way.

Quality Assurance (R10)

R10. The repository addresses technical quality and standards compliance, and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality-related evaluations.

Was: 11. Data quality. R11. The repository has appropriate expertise to address technical data and metadata quality and ensures that sufficient information is available for end users to make quality related evaluations.

Repository quality assurance is often related to 'standards compliance'. The requirement is intended to demonstrate that the repository provides data and metadata of sufficient 'technical quality'. This should be sufficient to allow users to make assessments about their 'scientific quality'. References to 'expertise' are removed to avoid overlap with Expertise & Guidance (R06)

Workflows (R11)

R11. Digital object management takes place according to defined workflows from deposit to access.

Was: 12. Workflows. R12. Archiving takes place according to defined workflows from ingest to dissemination.

The language of the Requirement has been updated to reflect that most commonly used within the applicant community.

Discovery and Identification (R12)

R12. The repository enables users to discover the digital objects and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation.

Was: 13. Data discovery and identification. R13. The repository enables users to discover the data and refer to them in a persistent way through proper citation.

Reuse (R13)

R13. The repository enables reuse of the digital objects over time, ensuring that appropriate information is available to support understanding and use.

Was: 14. Data reuse. R14. The repository enables reuse of the data over time, ensuring that appropriate metadata are available to support the understanding and use of the data.

Information Technology & Security

Storage & Integrity (R14)

R14. The repository applies documented processes to ensure data and metadata storage and integrity.

Was: 9. Documented storage procedures R9. The repository applies documented processes and procedures in managing archival storage of the data.

It was clear from previous applications that the topic of storage was addressed primarily in technical terms. This change moves Storage into the Information Technology and Security sub-section and unites it with integrity (previously included under R07) to cover the avoidance of unintended changes to data and metadata.

Technical Infrastructure (R15)

R15. The repository is managed on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and hardware appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.

Was: 15. Technical infrastructure R15. The repository functions on well-supported operating systems and other core infrastructural software and is using hardware and software technologies appropriate to the services it provides to its Designated Community.

Security (R16)

R16. The repository protects the facility and its data, metadata, products, services, and users.

Was: 16. Security. R16. The technical infrastructure of the repository provides for protection of the facility and its data, products, services, and users.